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Cocoa Value Chain Game

Analysis of trade, corporate governance, legal strategies, and development cooperation innovations to inform the development of transformative change pathways for biodiversity and equity

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Abstract

The Transformative Change for Biodiversity and Equity (TCforBE) project (2022 – 2026), supports transdisciplinary research to co-generate transformative change pathways in the context of telecoupled agrifood systems. It engages diverse stakeholders and explore plural perspectives within the EU and partner countries of Cameroon, Colombia, and Kenya, including EU and national policymakers and Indigenous Peoples and local communities. The project aims to strengthen stakeholder capacity on transformative change pathways leading to enhanced biodiversity and equity outcomes. Work package (WP) 2 of the project specifically focuses on the governance pathways that can initiate transformative change from consumer countries, in particular the European Union.

As part of this deliverable (2.2) we analysed trade, corporate governance, legal strategies, and development cooperation innovations to inform the development of transformative change pathways for biodiversity and equity. This report details the development of serious game to provide a case of the levers for change on biodiversity and equity and conditions for success in the cocoa sector originating from Cameroon. Defined as “games for research and not for leisure”, serious games use game theory and competitive resource allocation theories to explore the behaviour of systems, devise strategies and assess their strengths, and to support negotiations for collective and coordinated action. Numerous initiatives have been implemented to address the negative socio-environmental impacts of the cocoa value chain—such as laws, policies, regulations, market mechanisms (certifications and labelling), and social movements. We analyze which of these mechanisms, or a combination of them, might yield more positive biodiversity and equity outcomes along the value chain. This is in a context where the institutional and legal context for the exportation of cocoa to the consumer markets is changing, with the introduction of the EU Deforestation Regulation and Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence regulation.

Participatory research methods have previously been employed to incorporate diverse values and perspectives from stakeholders on various contested topics such as land use change, biodiversity loss, and poverty. An advantage of these methods is that they consider the positionality of stakeholders and the power dynamics between them. We recognize that knowledge inequities exist and reinforce negative power dynamics. By engaging with stakeholders and co-designing solutions, while facilitating knowledge exchange between groups like farmers and policymakers through unconventional and less confrontational methods (such as games), we aim to foster more equitable and systematic knowledge sharing, enabling diverse voices to be heard and driving transformative change. Using the CAMPOD- Cocoa value Chain Game we analyze the impacts that diverse existing and future initiatives on biodiversity and equity might have among the value chain, and particularly for producers and producing landscapes. Further games are planned to be played using this approach in Europe and in Cameroon.

The case provided in this report aids subsequent tasks of this WP and in D2.2, which examines deeper different governance pathways. In combination with WP 1 and WP3, this work package 2 contributes to envisioning an EU consumer country perspective on transformative change of food systems towards biodiversity and equity in producing countries (WP4, WP5).

Background

TCforBE Project Summary

Demand for agricultural commodities from EU agrifood systems is driving land use change in biodiversity-rich countries in the Global South, leading to major biodiversity losses. Globalisation processes have led to increases in EU imports of commodities such as soya and palm oil. EU trade has become increasingly ‘telecoupled’, i.e. characterised by distant, coupled human and natural systems via highly inequitable global value chains, which have extensive socioeconomic and environmental impacts.

Tackling the EU's global biodiversity footprint is a top EU policy priority. Transformative change pathways are needed for safe and just transitions; but there are plural perspectives on what might constitute transformative change for food territories and systems, including telecoupled ones, and how to achieve it. New EU policies, such as Farm to Fork, may significantly re-shape agrifood trade between the EU and producer countries, with a range of potential implications for employment, livelihoods, but also equity, justice, and biodiversity. Much depends upon the purpose of the food system or territory, but there is contestation on potential food futures at different scales. There are increasing calls for systemic levers, but barriers to action are significant.

The Transformative Change for Biodiversity and Equity (TCforBE) project², (2022 – 2026), will support transdisciplinary research to co-generate transformative change pathways in the context of telecoupled agrifood systems. It will engage diverse stakeholders and explore plural perspectives within the EU and partner countries of Cameroon, Colombia and Kenya, including EU and national policymakers and Indigenous Peoples and local communities. The project aims to strengthen stakeholder capacity on transformative change pathways leading to enhanced biodiversity and equity outcomes.

Underpinned by multi-stakeholder social learning cycles and attention to plural values, the researchers will seek to co-generate and co-analyse transformative change pathways at different scales for highly telecoupled landscapes and to facilitate dialogues between landscape actors and national and EU scales. To inform these learning cycles and dialogues, researcher driven activities will enrich the landscape and national learning processes and contribute to an overall analysis of transformative change pathways in telecoupled contexts. Envisaged research and learning activities include:

- Conceptual work on transformative change and biodiversity and equity pathways in telecoupled food and agriculture contexts, and synthesis and analysis of findings.
- Exploration of plural perspectives on transformative change at EU, national and landscape scales through qualitative research.
- Social learning cycles at landscape scale: participant-driven learning to co-generate transformative change pathways for food systems and territories (creative learning activities) and to inform/reflect upon planned researcher-led activities (e.g. rural imaginaries research, Bayesian tool development, case studies of corporate and regenerative enterprises). Analysis and social learning on plural perspectives on transformative change at national scale and identification of land use change drivers (e.g. commodity impacts, at-risk biodiversity hotspots, and sustainable landscape initiative impacts).
- A global dialogue, facilitated by the Global Landscapes Forum, will link the transdisciplinary processes between the scales, supported by additional dissemination and communication activities.
- Generation of scenarios and modelling of EU agrifood systems transformations.
- Analysis of interconnected processes and levers including EU biodiversity governance, trade, legal, consumer, collective action and sustainable finance levers and social innovations.

TCforBE aims and objectives

Demand for agricultural commodities from EU agrifood systems is driving land use change in biodiversity-rich countries in the Global South, leading to major biodiversity losses. Globalisation processes have led to increases in EU imports of commodities such as soya and palm oil. EU trade has become increasingly 'telecoupled', i.e. characterised by distant, coupled human and natural systems via highly inequitable global value chains, which have extensive socioeconomic and environmental impacts.

Tackling the EU's global biodiversity footprint is a top EU policy priority. Transformative change pathways are needed for safe and just transitions; but there are plural perspectives on what might constitute transformative change for food territories and systems, including telecoupled ones, and on how to achieve it. New EU policies, such as Farm to Fork, may significantly re-shape agrifood trade between the EU and producer countries, with a range of potential implications for employment, livelihoods, but also equity, justice, and biodiversity. Much depends upon the purpose of the food system or territory, but there is contestation on potential food futures at different scales. There are increasing calls for systemic levers, but barriers to action are significant.

The Transformative Change for Biodiversity and Equity (TCforBE) project², (2022 – 2026), will support **transdisciplinary research to co-generate transformative change pathways in the context of telecoupled agrifood systems**. It will engage diverse stakeholders and explore plural perspectives within the EU and partner countries of Cameroon, Colombia, and Kenya, including EU and national policymakers and Indigenous Peoples and local communities. The project aims to strengthen stakeholder capacity on transformative change pathways leading to enhanced biodiversity and equity outcomes.

The project aims to inform policy discourse, e.g. the EU's Green Deal implementation, and especially the Farm to Fork Strategy, which aims to reduce the environmental and climate footprint of the EU food system and its climate resilience, and specifically responds to expert scientific advice that highlights a particular need for more social science evidence on **how to achieve a sustainable food system**. The project will generate such evidence, as well as contributions from and to environmental science on biodiversity measurement and valuation.

The project will also engage national policymakers and seek to inform landscape stewardship strategies in study landscapes in Africa and Latin America.

TCforBE contributes to four HORIZON EUROPE specific outcomes: 1) Sustainable pathways, 2) human dimensions, 3) social norms, behaviours, values, and 4) inform/motivate transformational change. The project work packages (WPs) address all the outcomes in a cross-cutting way and are arranged according to *scale of interest* (e.g. EU and global, national producer countries, landscape levels).

There are seven **work packages** addressing the project's specific objectives (Box 1), each with associated results and deliverables:

- WP 1 will generate insights on EU policies and societal shifts under new green policies in relation to food systems and modelling of potential impacts on relevant biomes.
- WP 2 explores transformative governance arrangements and levers for change. This includes analysis of trade and legal levers, social movements and collective action, and biodiversity governance initiatives, as well as identifying the best ways to engage with EU and other scale learning and communications stakeholders.
- WP 3 will summarise the taxonomy and related regulations targeting and enabling Biodiversity measurement and develop sustainable finance pathways that are aggregable and scalable to impact and transform current mainstream finance logics.
- WP 4 – national scale engagement and research – identification of current visions of future relating to food and territories (Q methodology), followed by social processes and researcher-led activities to co-frame and co-learn on transformative change pathways including generation of scenarios, geospatial mapping of commodity and policy impacts.
- WP 5 – landscape scale engagement and research - activities as in WP4, but the transformative change pathways will include generation of a Bayesian tool drawing on Q methodology and social learning, corporate/regen case studies, rural imaginaries (political ecology and ethnography).
- WP 6 will involve a conceptual framing, but also synthesis of findings and support for inter-landscape and global / EU dialogues on transformative change pathways.
- WP7 concerns management, dissemination and communication of the project.

Box 1: TCforBE Specific Objectives

Objective 1: Deepen understanding and capacity of agrifood policymakers on transformative pathways for biodiversity and equity in EU telecoupled agrifood systems,.

Objective 2: Identify, assess, and engage EU policymakers and stakeholders on demand-side consumer country governance arrangements for transformative change in telecoupled EU agrifood systems for positive biodiversity and equity outcomes.

Objective 3: Analyse and assess the potentials and limitations of existing biodiversity metrics, measurements, and finance levers (EU Action 68) and derive innovative financial instruments to achieve high biodiversity business transformations that are aggregable and scalable to impact and transform current mainstream finance logics (EU Actions 72 and 73).

Objective 4: Identify, co-analyse, and assess, with policymakers and stakeholders, national supply side producer country policies, scenarios and transformative change pathways for biodiversity and equity.

Objective 5: To co-generate transformative change pathways for sustainable and regenerative landscapes, with high biodiversity and equity outcomes, drawing on new evidence and tools on biodiversity imaginaries, commodity impacts, SLI effectiveness/impacts, and corporate/regenerative enterprise.

Objective 6: Synthesise evidence and build global, regional and landscape learning to foster transformative change on biodiversity

All work packages will engage with communications, WP7 has a particular focus on making the knowledge, tools and methods generated by the project available to global audiences through appropriate media, to inform policy dialogues and learning. The transformative change pathways for landscape approaches, will be shared with and disseminated to policymakers, researchers, and agrifood system stakeholders.

TCforBE overall approach.

The overall approach is underpinned by **multi-stakeholder social learning cycles** and ensuring attention is given to plural values. The researchers will seek to cogenerate and co-analyse transformative change pathways at different scales for highly telecoupled landscapes and to facilitate dialogues between landscape actors and national and EU level stakeholders. To inform these learning cycles and dialogues, researcher driven activities will enrich the landscape and national level learning processes and contribute to an overall analysis of transformative change pathways in telecoupled contexts (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Components of the TCforBE Project

The envisaged research and learning activities include:

- Conceptual work on transformative change and biodiversity and equity pathways in telecoupled food and agriculture contexts, and synthesis and analysis of findings.
- Generation of scenarios and modelling of EU agrifood systems transformations. Understanding the potential implications of EU policy and societal transitions for low- and middle-income countries that link to the EU through telecoupling is vital as dietary shifts are already occurring and policy decisions are being made which may reduce or change EU country sourcing patterns.
- Exploration of plural perspectives on transformative change at EU, national and landscape scales through qualitative research.
- Analysis of interconnected processes and levers including EU biodiversity governance, trade, legal, consumer, collective action and sustainable finance levers and social innovations.)
- Analysis and social learning on plural perspectives on transformative change at national scale and identification of land use change drivers (e.g. commodity impacts, at-risk biodiversity hotspots, and sustainable landscape initiative impacts.)
- Social learning cycles at landscape scale: participant-driven learning to co-generate transformative change pathways for food systems and territories (creative learning activities) and to inform/reflect upon planned researcher-led activities.

D2.2 Cocoa value chain game

- A global dialogue, facilitated by the Global Landscapes Forum, will link the transdisciplinary processes between the scales, supported by additional dissemination and communication activities.

Table 1 The Study Producer Countries and Landscapes

Country	Landscapes	Landscape characteristics
Cameroon	Dja-Tridom	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emerging cocoa agrofood systems export timber and non-timber forest products (NTFP) trade, mining • Medium-high levels of telecoupling • Sustainability landscape initiatives (SLI) e.g. Dja Green cocoa landscape • Large areas of rapidly degrading high-biodiversity forests, increasing agriculture
Colombia	Eastern Plains Llanos Orientales Magdalena River Cauca River	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agricultural expansion for palm oil, cattle ranching, and reforestation programs. • Megadiverse landscapes • 20% in conservation and 30% in communal lands but facing violence, illicit economies, and weak state presence. • Appropriation of public lands, encroachment into natural parks, local elites driving deforestation, displacement of smallholders
Kenya	Mau forest – Masai - Mara river basin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wetlands - expanding rice production and fish farming, and grasslands with grazing systems • High biodiversity forests, conservation areas • Tea-avocado-fruit-livestock-timber-NTFP-horticulture systems • Medium levels of telecoupling • Large areas of high biodiversity forest ecosystems & extensive agriculture • Regenerative change & SLIs: MaMaSe program
	Mt Kenya	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grasslands (grazing systems) and tea-fruit-livestock-timber-horticulture systems • High biodiversity forests, conservation areas • Large areas high biodiversity forests, protected areas & extensive agriculture • Medium-high levels of telecoupling • SLIs: Mt Kenya Forest Landscape Restoration

Glossary

See [TC4BE glossary](#) for key terms and definitions

I. Introduction Cameroon to EU cocoa value chain

The Cameroonian cocoa industry is embedded within a value chain marked by a significant and growing concentration of corporate power in trading, processing, and manufacturing. This concentration leads to adverse social and environmental effects such as violations of human and labor rights, low farmer incomes, and poverty (Squicciarini & Swinnen, 2016). The industry's power dynamics also contribute to environmental degradation, dependence on global markets, and the weakening of democratic structures (Ingram et al., 2018; Busquet et al., 2021; Waarts & Kiewisch, 2021).

Despite the numerous initiatives implemented to address the negative socio-environmental impacts of the cocoa value chain—such as laws, policies, regulations, market mechanisms (certifications and labelling), and social movements—there is a need to analyze which of these mechanisms, or a combination of them, might yield more positive biodiversity and equity outcomes along the value chain.

In a context where the institutional and legal context for the exportation of cocoa to the consumer markets is changing, with the introduction of the EU Deforestation Regulation (EUDR- [Regulation on Deforestation-free products - European Commission \(europa.eu\)](https://european-council.europa.eu/media/en/press-room/item/30244?lang=en) and the Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence (CSDD- [Corporate sustainability due diligence - European Commission \(europa.eu\)](https://european-council.europa.eu/media/en/press-room/item/30244?lang=en)), we analyse the impacts that these and other initiatives might have on the producing landscapes in Cameroon.

Defined as “games for research and not for leisure”, serious games use game theory and competitive resource allocation theories to explore the behaviour of systems, devise strategies and assess their strengths, and to support negotiations for collective and coordinated action (Speelman et al., 2017).

Participatory research methods have previously been employed to incorporate diverse values and perspectives from stakeholders on various contested topics such as land use change, biodiversity loss, and poverty (Van Noordwijk et al., 2023). One of the major advantages of these methods is that they consider the positionality of stakeholders and the power dynamics between them. We recognize that knowledge inequities exist and reinforce negative power dynamics. By engaging with stakeholders and co-designing solutions, while facilitating knowledge exchange between groups like farmers and policymakers through unconventional and less confrontational methods (such as art and games), we aim to foster more equitable and systematic knowledge sharing, enabling diverse voices to be heard and driving transformative change.

The **Cocoa Value chain Game** aims to analyze the impacts that diverse existing and future initiatives on biodiversity and equity might have among the value chain, and particularly for producers and producing landscapes.

The Cocoa Value chain Game is set up to be implemented with diverse stakeholders (Producers, Intermediaries, Governments, NGOs, social movements) among cocoa value chain in producing (Cameroon) and consuming countries (EU).

The results enable us to identify and compare the most effective interventions for promoting biodiversity and equity in the cocoa value chain. Additionally, through the game and subsequent discussions with participants, we aim to uncover the challenges and opportunities associated with each intervention. We will also identify common values, perceptions, and motivations that can inform the design and implementation of more sustainable value chains.

2. Cocoa Value Chain Game

This game was developed as part of a collaboration between University of Applied Sciences Bern, LEAF Inspiring Change and Wageningen University & Research. A first draft was created by Nastasia Boul-Lefeuve in May 2023 together with researchers, practitioners, and cocoa producers in Cameroon. Further development took place through desk research, testing with researchers and game designers in Wageningen and the game which was played with a public audience at Amsterdam Cocoa Week in February 2024.

2.1 Game instructions

General rules

- The game is played in 6 rounds, each representing 1 year.
- There are 5 cocoa producers, 1 cooperative, 1 coxneur, 2 buyers and 1 certification organisation as active players in the game.
- The landscape is defined by dense forest (6 plots), savanna (3 plots) and cocoa plantations (9 plots). The cocoa plantations have different age stages, ranging from young (Y), to mature (M1, M2) to old (O).
- Sustainability indicators (economic, social and environmental) are used so that all players can monitor performance and compliance with national objectives.
 - Economic indicator - export objective of 24 units of cocoa per year, increased to 30 by the end of the game.
 - Social indicator – schooling rate: 10 kids attending school.
 - Environmental indicator – forest cover: initial forest cover of 12 trees.

Materials and facilitation

The game is facilitated by a team of 2 facilitators: one main facilitator as a game master, and one assistant-facilitator to support data collection, money handling, participants' accompaniment and note taking during debriefing.

For scientific data collection, a third person is recommended.

Rules

In total, at least 10 players are needed for each session of the **Cocoa Value chain Game**. More people can participate, playing in pairs. The different characters are described in Table 2.

Room setting

Table 2 Player descriptions

Role	Description
Cocoa producer 1	Your family is rich. You own 3 cocoa plantations. The annual cost to take care of your family and plantations are 2200 F.
Cocoa producer 2-3	Your family is wealthy. You own 2 cocoa plantations. The annual cost to take care of your family and plantations are 1500 F
Cocoa producer 4-5	You own 1 cocoa plantation. You also hunt in the nearby forest to bring home food and cash. The annual cost to take care of your family and plantations are 800 F.
Coxeur	You buy cocoa directly from the producer at the farm gate and trade it with buyers. The annual production and maintenance costs is: $500F + 50F \times \text{number of cocoa units bought}$ You buy the cocoa from the producers in cash.
Cooperative	You are the representative of the village cooperative. You own 1 storage whose capacity is 12 cocoa units /year. The annual production and maintenance costs for your storage is: $300F + 50F \times \text{number of cocoa units bought}$ You make a contract with farmers to get their cocoa.
Buyer World	You buy cocoa from a coxeur and the cooperative to sell them at the port in Douala for exportations on the world markets. You have 2 lines of trucks to transport the cocoa to the port. Your annual maintenance costs are $500 \times \text{nb of transportation capacities}$.
Buyer EU	You buy cocoa from a coxeur and a cooperative who sell at the port in Douala for export to world markets. You have 2 lines of trucks to transport the cocoa to the port. Your annual maintenance costs are $500 \times \text{nb of transportation capacities}$.
Certification Organisation	You are a certification body and labelling organisation that guarantees a product fulfils certain environmental and social standards. You can only certify actors from the formal markets, such as producers, cooperatives und buyers. You are still developing the criteria for your label, and are looking into international frameworks, and calls from advocacy organisations in consumer countries. Once your certification standard is established, you will undertake risk assessments, issue certifications, and perform audits to ensure the certified actors comply with your standards. Your annual operating costs are minimum 500F or $500 \times \text{number of certifications, audits, reports undertaken}$.

Description of player's actions

In Table 3, the roles during the **Cocoa Value chain Game** for each of the players are described. Players are informed of these roles, with information given to them on a card.

Table 3 Description of the roles of each of the players during the game

Role	How it works	Comment on likely dynamics
Producers	<p>Producers can decide how to manage their cocoa yield, by investing in</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Densification • Rejuvenation • Inputs <p>Producers sell to Coxeur or Cooperative.</p> <p>Producers – if they have no other option, can lower their living costs, if they take their kids out of school to work in their plantations. This does not increase the yield, but it lowers their living costs by 100/child/round. Putting the child back doesn't cost anything, but increases their living costs again.</p> <p>Producers cannot sell to Buyers directly, except for if producers officially (<i>hence: admitted by facilitator</i>) form an own cooperative → they have to collectively pay 50*cocoa units as maintenance costs.</p> <p>If producers want to get certification, they have to invest in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trained workforce (+1 yield/round): 400/round • What other benefits they get, will be subject of decision/discussion by the certification body. <p>If producers want to provide any information about their land, they will have to pay 50/field.</p>	<p>Big producer is likely to have a rather easy life.</p> <p>Producers with Young / Old plantations are struggling a lot. Those with Young plantations will improve in Round 3, when their field becomes Mature.</p> <p>Apart from the Big producer, they likely cannot afford certification, and will need support for that.</p>
Cooperative	<p>The cooperative buys cocoa on a contract bases, paying the producers with a time delay.</p> <p>The cooperative is the only one that can get certification (the coxeur cannot).</p> <p>Cooperatives can sell to World Market and to EU buyer.</p>	<p>Performance of cooperative depends on how well they pay the farmers, and how well they negotiate with buyers – it can go fairly well, or quite difficult.</p> <p>Getting certification might be difficult.</p>
Coxeur	<p>Coxeurs buy directly in cash from producers, and sell to the buyers.</p> <p>The Coxeur cannot become certified, which might restrict their selling channels, especially if the EU buyer makes certification a prerequisite.</p>	<p>In this game, the coxeur will start quite easy in the game. He will be lending out money to the producers, help them invest in their fields, make deals.</p> <p>It's a crucial role in the game for the producers.</p>
Buyer World	<p>The world buyer will buy whatever cocoa is available, if he has the capacity.</p> <p>Price for cocoa on the World Market is announced at the beginning of the Round.</p>	

D2.2 Cocoa value chain game

Role	How it works	Comment on likely dynamics
Buyer EU	<p>In the first round, the EU buyer will have freedom to buy all cocoa available.</p> <p>Starting from round 2, the EU buyer will have to comply with EU regulations on Deforestation and XX. Their maintenance costs increase by 100/unit.</p> <p>In order to fulfill it's due diligence, the EU buyer will be asked to show a Risk Statement and submit Information on the sourcing of their Cocoa.</p> <p>At market price, this costs 1000 to produce it, and has to be renewed annually at 500.</p>	
Certification Body	<p>The certification body can only certify cooperatives, producers and Buyers. The certification has a set standard that producers, cooperatives and buyers have to comply with. They will define these criteria during the first round.</p> <p>It can include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No forest conversion • No deforestation by plantation owners • No child work • Guaranteed prices on cooperative level or on buyer level • Premiums <p>The certification body offers services to help buyers comply with the regulations, at a negotiated price, either linked to a certification or not.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk assessments to Buyers: • Certification: • Training to the producers: 	
Certification/ Labelling	<p>Certification can be provided by the Certification Body.</p> <p>It costs 500 to get the certification (once). Additionally, the producers have to invest in trained labor force, which will also increase their yield.</p>	<p>Making trained labor force mandatory shall show the required investments farmers have to make, while also showing that this does most probably increase their yields (although this will also depend on whether they actually do the best practices or not in reality).</p>
Forest	<p>Starting with 6 forest patches with 12 logs. If forest cover is < 6, then living costs increase by +50, if < 3, then living costs increase by +100.</p>	
School kids	<p>Schooling is mandatory in Cameroon. If producers have problems with cashflow, they can take kids out of school to 1) reduce their living costs by 20% or 2) to increase their capacity (1 free workforce)</p>	

D2.2 Cocoa value chain game

Documents environmental and social indicators.

- Forest Cover in the landscape
- Densification of Cocoa plantations (decrease in biodiversity)
- Schooling Rate (i.e. Child Labor)

Game Schedule + Round Sequences

In the following tables, the Schedule of the game and the sequence of each round are described.

Table 4 Game Schedule

Agenda item	Time	Content
Welcome + Icebreaker	15 min	Welcome participants, short introduction round Spectrograph: how familiar with cocoa value chain vs games
Briefing Game	10 min	Explain the game, roles, rules
Round 1	20 min	First round, usually takes a bit longer, as it is a learning round
Round 2-4	30 min (10 min/R)	
Round 5	15 min	End of R4/Beginning of R5: Conference to discuss new measures. 5min Discussion time. Then play normal round.
End of Game	= 90 min	
Debriefing	30-60 min	Ensure at least 30 min, better 45-60 min for an in-depth debriefing of the game.
Total	2-3 hours	2 hours seems very short, make sure it is rather 2.5 to 3 hours to ensure enough time for discussion and reflection.

Table 5 Round Sequence

Phase	Time	Producers	Buyer, Cooperative	Coxeur,	Certification Organisation
Announcement		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cocoa Exporting Price is announced. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 800 / 850 / 750 (depending on production levels) • Scenario Announcement 			
Investments		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cash-in contracts from cooperative • Buy inputs • Densification / rejuvenation of plantation • Conversion of plantation • Certification / Trainings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cooperative pays out the contracts to producers • Cooperative + coxeur negotiate with buyers and/or producers 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussions, risk assessments, etc. • Certifications
Harvesting		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Negotiations with coxeur + cooperative 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Negotiations with producers & buyers 		

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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sell cocoa to cooperative or coxeur 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cooperative + coxeur buy cocoa from producers 	
Sales + Payment of costs		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pay expenses 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Buyers buys cocoa from coxeur + cooperative Export to markets Pay expenses 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Auditing Pay expenses
Board update		Plantation ageing (every 2 nd round) Forest re-growth		

Scenarios

In table 6, the different scenarios of the game enacted in each round are described.

Table 6 Game Scenarios per round

Round	Description
Round 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No specific scenario – production and selling
Round 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Price still 800F. New national objective to increase cocoa production (to 30). New EU regulations have been adopted on Deforestation and Corporate Sustainability, binding implementation starting R3-R4. Information is published at the Ports for those interested. Pitch by the certification organisation.
Round 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EU Regulations have to be implemented now. EU Regulations will ban products linked to Deforestation and Human Rights Abuse from EU market. Suppliers will have to make present a Risk Statement and Geo References that their products are deforestation free along the whole value chain. Suppliers have to invest in Assessments, and their annual maintenance costs will increase by 100F/transportation line.
Round 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Global cocoa supplies are struggling to cover the demand due to crises in fertiliser supplies, and poor cocoa yields due to climate change induced pests. The market price for Cocoa has increased to 850. <p>End of round:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Report by Consumer-NGO: monitors compliance and points out that there is problems in the value chain <p>→ Swiss Development Cooperation organizes a national conference to discuss measures.</p>
Round 5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nothing
Other scenarios	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> As a supporting measure, the Team Europe Initiative supports afforestation efforts by providing free tree seedlings for reforestation and protection of forested area to smallholders. CAM government makes a campaign to increase productivity, and provides cheap cocoa tree seedlings → Rejuvenation available at 300-500F Shortage of Cocoa on European Markets → price on EU market increases Disaster: small yields

Overview players & starting conditions

In table 7, the initial conditions of each of the players at the beginning of the game are described.

Table 7 Starting conditions of each of the players

Players	Nr of players	Nr of plots per player	Plot age, start	Starting money (CFA)	Living costs F	Initial production w/out investment	Recommended price F
Big farmer	1	3	M1	800	2200	7	
Medium farmer	2	2	M2, Y	500	1500	4, 3	
Small farmer	2	1	M2, O	300	800	2, 1	
Coxeur	1			2000	300 + 50*units		< 550 / unit
Cooperative	1			0	300 + 50*units	2 * 6 units (12)	400-600 / unit
Buyer World	1			2500	500*lines	2 * 5 units (10)	550-700 / unit
Buyer EU	1			2500	500*lines	2 * 5 units (10)	
Certification Body	1			1000	500*nr of certifications/ audits/reports		

Cocoa Yield Management

In table 8, cocoa yield management for each of the stages of the cocoa plantation is shown. The changes in yield management occur in each round of the game.

Table 8 Cocoa yield management

Cocoa Yield			
	Dens 1	Dens 2	Dens 3
Y Young (0-7)	1	2	3
M1 Mature (7-14)	2	3	4
M2 Mature (14-25)	2	3	4
O Old (25-60)	1	2	3

Inputs & standard practices : +1

Trained workforce (best practices): +1

Table 9 World market prices

Market supply levels	Units	Price on Global Market
Medium	17-20 units	800
High	> 20 units	750
Low	< 17 units	850

Table 10 Producer market prices

Cost Item	Price (CFF)	Influence in the game
Inputs (chemicals + labor)	400	Increases cocoa yield +1 Valid for 1 round
Trained workforce (mandatory for certified producers)	400	Increases cocoa yield +1 Valid for 1 round
Densification	1000	Increases cocoa yield +1 Valid for rest of the game
New plantation (= forest conversion)	1000 + 700F increase in living costs	Will have influence on producer's living cost, and on compliance with EU regulations
Timber log	200	F = 10 If F < 6, costs for producer increase by +50 If F < 3, costs for producer increase by +100
Rejuvenation	1000	Keeps plantation in in M1/M2 for 2 more rounds Valid for rest of the game
Reforestation (per forest patch)	1000	Natural regeneration: 1 tree / round Reforestation: t+1 influence on smallholder costs
Certification	500 (first time)	

Table 11 Cooperatives and Buyers market prices

Item	Price (F)	
Extra storage / transport capacity	1000	
Due Diligence Reporting	1000	
Risk Assessment	1000	

D2.2 Cocoa value chain game

Certification		Certifies compliance with standards (to be set by CBO)
Obtain Certification	1000 (first time)	
Annual Audit	500/year	Can help Buyer EU to comply with EU standards

Table 12 Certification Organisation Market prices

Item	Price (F)	
Perform an audit, Risk assessment, Due Diligence Report	300F increase in living costs	
Issue a certification	300F increase in living costs	

Background information for participants

- Average size of plantation in Cameroon: 1ha -4ha
- Density of plantation: on average 300-500 plants/ha, with a maximum of up to 1200 plants
- Cameroon's export objective: 600.000t cocoa/year, with a current production of less than 300.000 t/year
- Imports / global competition with Indonesia and Latin America
- Strategies to improve cocoa production on field are:
 - Densification
 - Rejuvenation
 - Labour
 - Inputs

Table 12. Background information of the production system

Forest	Cocoa	Yield	
200 trees	1200 trees	from 1T to 3T	Increased Densification
600 trees	600 trees	300-500kg	Current system

- Land conversion: costs ca. 200.000 FCFA/ha

Table 13 Plantation ageing and change in yield

	0-7 years	7-14	14-25	25-60
Standard practices	60%	100%	decreasing	decreasing
Good practices	60%	100%	100%	decreasing

- Access to financing is difficult for cooperatives and producers. The only cash lenders are input sellers who demand high interest rates.
- Coxeurs are emergency contacts for producers, they may support producers in emergency situations, not necessarily with lending money, but by paying upfront.
- Buyer: The buyer is the one that owns the transport and comes to the village to discuss the prices with the coxeur and the cooperative. He is the one that earns the most according to interviewees. The buyer has capacity constraints, can't buy all the cocoa of both the coxeur and the cooperative, and therefore has the bargaining power to buy at a lower price. We have only played with one buyer, but we were discussing integrating a 2nd buyer, for more competition - which can become after 2 or 3 rounds, an organic buyer - working with only certified product.
- Game prices of cocoa along the value chain
 - Farmers : 1000F/kg
 - Cooperative/ Coxeur : 1200F/KG
 - Buyer: 1500F
 - Exporter: 1700-1800F
- Scenarios of interest:
 - Impact of EU Deforestation Regulations (EUDR) on cocoa production, land use change and prices in the system
 - Impact of certification programs introduced by Buyers (e.g. at 65F)
 - Changes in interactions if appearance of Chocolatier as Direct Buyer

2.2 Data collection

Data can be collected at national, player and landscape levels:

National indicators:

- Environmental Indicator:
 - Forest Cover: deforestation
 - Densification of cocoa production: decrease in biodiversity
- Social Indicator: Schooling Rate: child work
- Economic Indicator:
 - Export to EU market
 - Export to World market

Player level indicators:

- Producers:

Investments

- Inputs
- Densification
- Rejuvenation
- Certification
- Trained labor force
- Cooperative:
 - Amount of cocoa bought by producer
 - Price paid to producer
 - Number of cocoa sold to buyer + price
 - Certification
 - Services / premiums to producers

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- Coxeur:
 - Cocoa sold to buyer
 - Services provided to farmers
 - Buyer World:
 - Buyer EU:
- Investments
- Certification
 - Cocoa exports to market

Landscape

- Forest cover

3. Results of the Cocoa value chain game, Amsterdam Cocoa Week 8th February 2024

An announcement to participate in the game was published on [LinkedIn](#) to coincide with publicity around Chocoa. [Chocoa](#) is a major international cocoa and chocolate event for stakeholders in the sector. Chocoa is now part of the Amsterdam Cocoa Week. Invites to participate were also sent via email to organizations, enterprises and networks in the cocoa sector. This resulted in visitors to Chocoa indicating their interest, of which 12 players participated from the cocoa industry including traders, a certification organisation, and researchers. The game was played on 8th February 2024 during Chocoa. In total, only the first three rounds out of the five rounds that were planned were played. A sustainability certification scheme was introduced as planned, at the beginning of the second round.

Some of the main results were:

- From round 1 to the end, social inequalities were persistent as those producers that have small cocoa producing areas (Players 4 and 5), were running out of economic resources, which jeopardized their development in subsequent rounds. In the second round, these producers were the first that took children out of school, and the ones that were deforesting to produce more cocoa for supplying the international markets. Small holder producers of the game were always in debt and unable to afford the certifications, supplying the cocoa to the international markets.
- In contrast, wealthier producers (1-3) had more chances to buy certifications and export the cocoa to the EU, when the new law was implemented. They only took one or two children out of school during the game, they access the EU market, and the certification scheme.
- Collective action and common decisions were absent during the whole game. Wealthier producers negotiated directly the prices of cocoa with the intermediaries (coxeur and cooperative) and with the certification organisation.
- No one was concerned about the loss of the vegetation in rounds 2 and 3. Short term economic gains were the priority of all players.

Sustainability indicators

Key economic, social, and environmental indicators to monitor the performance and compliance with national objectives in Cameroon, as a proxy of the impacts of the EUDR and the certification schemes are presented.

Economic indicators

- a) Export objective: 24 units of cocoa per year, increased to 30.
- b) During the game, the target was not reached. At the end of the third-round producers were able to export 19 units of cocoa to the EU (9 seeds) and the international (10 seeds) markets.

Figure 2 Economic: Amount of cocoa exported to international and EU markets during the game

D2.2 Cocoa value chain game

Social indicator

- Objective: To maintain the schooling rate by 10 kids attending school.
- From the first round, many children needed to leave the school for producing cocoa. At the end of the third round 50% of the children (6 children) were taken out of school.

Figure 3 Social indicator: Change in the number of children in school during the cocoa game

Environmental indicator

- Objective: To maintain forest cover (12 trees in total)
- From round two, all the trees were cut down because of the implementation of the EUDR in combination with the certification (Figure 3).

Figure 4 Environmental indicator: Evolution of the forest cover during the cocoa game

Recommendations

- Give a bit more of time for players to evaluate the game and embedded in the distinct roles they are playing., This time would be beneficial for the participants to get familiar with the rules of the game.
- Some elements of the game could be simplified such as the age of the plantations that change each of the rounds. This to simplify the rules and make the rules more comprehensible for participants.
- Give a time after each of the rounds, for the people who is helping to implement the game, to get information regarding the money, trees, cocoa, and children in school each of the participants have.
- Need a designated person to record the information, to play as the bank and to play as the international and EU markets each time. This person should be familiar with the aim of the game and the rules they could play.
- The coxeur had extra information about his role on the game. We need to think if we can standardize this role for future games.
- The benefit for having the certification scheme should be reflected in the game, adding some gains to farmers. This is what happens.
- The role of consumers could be introduced in another round of the game by, for example, adding some instructions to the markets such as “now EU consumers are worried about equity”. This could lead to farmers to organize themselves or not, for exporting to other markets. We most consider if this is the best way to include the effects of consumer on the cocoa value chain.
- Introducing the EUDR and the certification scheme at the same time, was quite chaotic. We recommend separating these interventions in different rounds, or in different games for the same audience. This is a decision that need to be taken regarding the financial aspects of the project.
- The discussion at the end could be standardized, for the results of different games to be able to compare.
- We need to encourage participants to fill up the follow up questionnaire at the end of the session and before the general reflection.

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